

ANALYSIS OF DIGITAL MARKETING COMMUNICATION MIX STRATEGIES FOR INDOMIE PRODUCTS: MULTICHANNEL INTEGRATION FOR OPTIMIZING BRAND ENGAGEMENT AND CONSUMER LOYALTY

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Abstract

The development of digital technology encourages companies to adopt more integrated and multi-channel marketing communication strategies to maintain competitiveness amidst increasingly fierce market competition. This study aims to analyze the effectiveness of the digital marketing communication mix implemented by Indomie through the "Hype Abis" campaign in increasing consumer engagement, brand awareness, sales, and customer loyalty. This study uses a qualitative approach with a literature review method of various scientific sources relevant to digital marketing communications, B2C, B2B, and C2B strategies, and consumer behavior in the instant noodle industry. The results of the study indicate that Indomie's multi-channel digital marketing strategy, including social media integration, collaboration with influencers, creative content based on digital culture trends, and optimization of e-commerce platforms, has proven effective in creating a viral effect, increasing sales, and strengthening emotional connections with consumers. In addition, active consumer participation through user-generated content (C2B) contributes to increased customer loyalty. Evaluation of campaign performance through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) is an important factor in ensuring the effectiveness of digital marketing communication strategies. This study recommends developing strategies through the use of innovative technology, data-driven approaches, strengthening digital loyalty programs, and expanding strategies to the B2B segment to support the sustainable growth of the Indomie brand.

Keywords: digital marketing communications; marketing mix; brand awareness; consumer loyalty; Indomie.

INTRODUCTION

Indomie, one of Indonesia's leading instant noodle brands, has successfully maintained its market leadership position through the implementation of innovative and adaptive marketing strategies (Irpansyah et al., 2023). The rapid development of digital technology in the modern era has encouraged companies to continuously innovate by implementing relevant and effective digital marketing strategies (Putri, 2022). Simultaneous campaigns, coupled with innovative product variants, are crucial for increasing consumer engagement and strengthening brand awareness through a multi-channel strategy (Anees-ur-Rehman et al., 2018). Previous research confirms that brand awareness plays a crucial role in influencing consumer decision-making. When brand awareness of a product increases, consumers are more likely to purchase that product (Irpansyah et al., 2023). Conversely, low levels of brand awareness efforts can lead to a decrease in consumer purchase interest in a company's products (Irpansyah et al., 2023). Furthermore, social media has been shown to significantly increase brand awareness, with its high connectivity linking consumers and communities (Putri, 2022). Another study, using Go-Jek's digital communication strategy in Samarinda, demonstrated that social media is a key platform for marketers to build brand awareness due to its ability to reach a broad audience and foster intense interactions (Putri, 2022). Furthermore, research by Anees-ur-Rehman et al. (2018) revealed that brand-oriented strategies significantly influence the financial performance of B2B SMEs. However, related literature is limited and often yields mixed findings. Therefore, their study examined the impact of brand-oriented strategies on financial performance through four constructs: internal branding, brand communication, brand awareness, and brand credibility.

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With technological advancements, digital marketing has become a primary choice for companies to reach potential customers. A study by Ningrum (2023) demonstrates how Sudut Lombok, a digital marketing business, implemented various strategies to increase brand awareness. This study aimed to identify the strategies used, measure the effectiveness of brand awareness, and formulate solutions for more optimal implementation of digital marketing strategies (Ningrum, 2023). In the context of nonprofit social marketing, research by Rudov et al. (2016) highlights the effectiveness of audience segmentation based on engagement patterns on campaign websites. This strategy helps brands increase brand awareness and create online buzz. Furthermore, research by Tripambudi (2023) analyzes the influence of brand image and advertising effectiveness on purchasing decisions for Supermie instant noodles in Gresik Regency. The results show that brand image and product quality have a significant positive influence on purchasing decisions.

Another study by Wartaka & Sumardjono (2020) used Fishbein multi-attribute analysis to understand consumer behavior when purchasing instant noodles. The study results showed that attributes such as flavor variety, ease of product access, halal certification, and ease of preparation were the main factors consumers considered. Furthermore, Indomie received the highest positive attitude score compared to other instant noodle brands, demonstrating Indomie's dominance in consumer choice. Recent research also examined the digital marketing strategies implemented by Lemonilo, a healthy instant noodle brand. Wijayanto (2023) explained how Lemonilo presents a distinct value proposition compared to its competitors, such as Indomie and Mie Sedaap. Research by Azizah & Damastuti (2023) also found that brand ambassadors, such as NCT Dream, play a crucial role in building Lemonilo's brand awareness, especially among the younger generation. Overall, various studies have provided a comprehensive overview of the importance of marketing strategies, both digital and conventional, in increasing brand awareness and influencing purchasing decisions. However, more in-depth research is needed to understand how Indomie, as the instant noodle market leader, has managed to maintain its dominance through the implementation of innovative and effective digital marketing strategies amidst increasingly fierce competition.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the ever-evolving digital era, marketing communications plays a strategic role in supporting marketing effectiveness and achieving corporate business goals (Alrianti & Iliyas, 2022; Wardani, 2023). Digital developments encourage companies to manage their marketing communications mix in a more integrated manner to optimally reach and influence their target market (Ningrum, 2023; Ramadhan & Chatamallah, 2022). Indomie, as one of the leading instant noodle brands in Indonesia, faces the challenge of determining the most appropriate digital marketing communications mix to maintain market dominance amidst increasingly fierce competition in the instant noodle industry (Arthantri, 2021; Wartaka & Sumardjono, 2020). Competition between instant noodle brands requires companies to continuously strengthen their brand image and the effectiveness of their marketing messages delivered to consumers (Tripambudi, 2023; Zahra, 2024).

In addition to the Business-to-Consumer (B2C) strategy, the Business-to-Business (B2B) approach also has the potential to support brand performance and sustainability through strategies oriented towards strengthening business value and relationships (Anees-ur-Rehman et al., 2018). Implementing a comprehensive marketing communications strategy that considers various approaches, including B2C and C2B, is a strategic step in increasing communication effectiveness towards various market segments (Wardani, 2023; Azizah & Achsa, 2021). Therefore, a systematic evaluation of the digital marketing communications mix is a crucial factor in measuring the success of a brand's marketing program (Rudov et al., 2016). With a deep understanding of digital marketing communications practices and consumer behavior, Indomie is expected to be able to optimize its strategies to reach a wider audience, increase customer loyalty, and strengthen the brand's position in the market (Wijayanto, 2023; Putri, 2022).

METHOD

This study uses a qualitative approach with a literature review method, aiming to gain a comprehensive understanding of the digital marketing communications mix and its application in the marketing strategies of instant noodle brands, particularly Indomie. The literature review method was chosen because it allows researchers to identify, analyze, and synthesize various relevant previous research findings to build a systematic and in-depth conceptual framework (Alrianti & Iliyas, 2022; Wardani, 2023). The data used in this study are secondary data obtained from various scientific literature sources, such as national and international journal articles, research reports, and scientific papers discussing marketing communications, the digital marketing communications mix,

Business-to-Consumer (B2C), Business-to-Business (B2B), and Consumer-to-Business (C2B) strategies. The use of secondary data in literature review research is considered effective in describing the development of marketing communications concepts and practices based on the results of previous research (Rudov et al., 2016; Azizah & Achsa, 2021). The literature collection process was carried out systematically by selecting relevant sources directly related to the research topic. The selected literature was then analyzed descriptively and qualitatively by grouping findings based on themes, variables, and digital marketing communication strategy approaches. This analysis aimed to identify patterns, similarities, and differences in research results, thereby drawing conclusions regarding the most effective digital marketing communication mix strategy in supporting Indomie's brand strengthening and marketing sustainability (Ningrum, 2023; Wijayanto, 2023). The results of the literature analysis were then synthesized to produce a structured understanding of the role of the digital marketing communication mix in reaching a wider audience, increasing consumer loyalty, and strengthening brand position amidst the increasingly competitive instant noodle industry (Arthantri, 2021; Tripambudi, 2023).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Most Beneficial Marketing Communication Mix for Indomie

Indomie's most beneficial marketing communications mix can be seen in its significant sales success. According to Indofood's 2023 Annual Report, Indomie's total sales grew 6%. The company stated that its bag noodle sales performance was maintained thanks to the launch of various new products and flavors, including the Indomie Ramen Series. To support this, the company implemented integrated above-the-line (ATL) and below-the-line (BTL) marketing activities to increase brand equity and brand loyalty. Data from topbrand-award.com shows that Indomie controls 71.20% of bag noodle consumption in Indonesia. The marketing communications mix used includes two main strategies: creative message development, media, and communications mix, as well as sales promotion, pop-up advertising, and sponsorship. The ATL strategy focuses on the use of mass media such as TV, radio, and digital advertising, which helps Indomie reach a wider audience while increasing brand awareness. Indomie advertisements frequently appear during prime time on national television and digital media such as YouTube, with creative campaigns for both regular and variant products. As stated by Amiarno (2022), the marketing mix, word of mouth, and brand image play a significant role in attracting repeat customers.

On the other hand, BTL strategies target activities closer to consumers through event sponsorships, sampling, and in-store product displays. For example, sponsorship of sporting events or culinary events targeting younger demographics, such as Hype Abis products. Ramadhan & Chatamallah (2022) emphasize that an effective marketing communication strategy consists of developing creative messages and appropriate media distribution. Furthermore, sales promotion strategies encourage direct sales through discounts, bundling, and retail promotions such as "Buy 2 Get 1 Free" programs. Point-of-sale promotional materials (POP materials), such as special displays in minimarkets, are also designed to attract consumer attention to Indomie products. The role of regular products and variations in Indomie's marketing strategy is also key to Indomie's success. Regular products such as Indomie Goreng, Kuah, and Jumbo form the backbone of sales because they are produced year-round, distributed evenly from large stores to MSMEs, and are the focus of ATL strategies to maintain consumer loyalty. Meanwhile, variation products such as Indomie Premium, Kuliner Indonesia, and Hype Abis are designed as flavor innovations that create "hype" in the market. These products are available for a limited time and are marketed more exclusively in medium-scale stores such as minimarkets, which drives added value and customer loyalty. Wardani (2023) states that implementing a comprehensive marketing communications mix can be key to achieving business goals. Supporting data from the Indofood Report and various studies demonstrate the effectiveness of Indomie's marketing communications strategy. Indomie's total sales grew 6% in 2023, and its market dominance of 71.20% demonstrates the successful integration of ATL and BTL. With a strategy that includes creativity in message development, effective promotions, and product innovation, Indomie has successfully maintained its dominant position in the Indonesian instant noodle market and maintained a positive growth rate despite increasingly fierce market competition.

1.1.1. Creative Strategies for Developing Messages, Media and Communication Mix

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The message development strategy in the Indomie campaign demonstrates consistency in creativity for each campaign theme, particularly the product variation campaign. The theme adapts to new product variants and the momentum that is currently developing and attracting public attention. In each program, Indomie creates a special design and a special message. The special design for each campaign program adapts to the product packaging being campaigned, including: color, writing, and certain symbols or shapes. These special designs are implemented in image/poster designs and pop-up stores established both indoors and outdoors. Examples of these special designs are as follows:

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Although each Indomie campaign program has its own tagline (#OhMyGoodItsIndomie, #HypeAbis, #RawonMerconEnakPol, #IndomieRamen), there is always Indomie's main tagline, namely "Indomie my taste" so that all product campaigns are always connected to each other. The arrangement of messages in each Instagram Feed also applies 8 (eight) Effective Key Messages attributes. The analysis of the application of each attribute in Instagram @indomie is presented in the following table:

Table 1 Marketing Communication Analysis

Attribute	Implementation	Analysis
Concise	The caption in each feed should contain no more than three sentences. The message structure is: a greeting to the audience, 1-3 sentences of the main message, and a closing invitation to the audience.	This makes the message focus on the core information that is to be conveyed and makes the audience understand it in no more than 30 seconds.
Strategic	Content is compiled based on trend analysis and target audience needs.	Messages are ensured to be relevant to the target audience, in line with trends and support the brand's goal of building loyalty.
Relevant	Content adapts to cultural trends and audience lifestyles.	Making the brand look current and relevant in the audience's daily lives, such as through the Hype Abis campaign.
Compelling	Use element visual and narrative that attracts the audience's attention.	The message conveyed creates emotional appeal and invites the audience to interact further.
Simple	Avoid complexity in delivering information.	The message is easy to understand and directly conveys the product's main benefits, as in the "Indomie Seleraku" advertisement.
Memorable	Taglines such as "Indomie Seleraku" and "Hype Abis" are used consistently across various campaigns.	Helping audiences remember brands easily through simple yet emotionally powerful elements.

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	Real	Content reflect consumers' real experiences with the product.	The use of user-generated content such as reviews and testimonials adds authenticity and credibility to the brand.
	Tailored	Messages and designs are tailored to each digital platform.	Ensuring audiences on Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube get a relevant and engaging experience across each platform.

Meanwhile, Indomie's media and communication mix for each campaign consistently utilizes a variety of media, from TV commercials, billboards, videotrons, to Indomie's social media accounts such as Instagram, X, and YouTube. According to the published 2023 PT Indofood Annual Report, the purpose of using this media mix, both on TV and various social media platforms, is to maintain high brand awareness and increase brand relevance to its diverse target consumers.

Indomie Korean Ramyeon advertisements displayed on videotrons at intersections and shopping centers have also become a source of advertising on social media. This can be seen on the accounts @kumparancom and @themaplemedia below:

Sales Promotion, POP Material, and Sponsorship

The Instagram account @rumahindofood reveals that Indomie sponsors several activities in various fields. The @rumahindofood Instagram account serves as a digital marketing communication tool for all Indofood products, publicizing and documenting Indofood's various sponsorship activities. In sports, Indomie sponsors badminton

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competitions, the Persib team, and the Bali United team. Other activities include free homecoming trips (mudik), Indomie Goes to School, and Indomie Sapa Santri (Sapa Santri). Indomie utilizes sponsorship across various activities to increase brand awareness. For activities with a more heterogeneous audience, Indomie focuses on publicizing regular products or the Indomie brand in general, as seen in sports activities and the free homecoming trip. Meanwhile, for activities with a more segmented audience, Indomie publishes product variations, such as the Sapa Santri and Indomie Goes to School activities (Batt et al., 2021; Jin, 2017).

Indomie's sales promotion strategy focuses on increasing consumer engagement through various direct promotional programs. Programs such as special discounts, product bundling, and "Buy 2 Get 1 Free" promotions are often found in minimarkets and retail stores, especially for variety products. These strategies aim to encourage impulse purchases and increase sales volume in the short term. Furthermore, Indomie also utilizes seasonal promotions, such as special Ramadan bundle packages or direct reward programs involving its products. These strategies not only drive sales but also create added value for Indomie products and maintain consumer engagement with the brand (Syed, 2023; Firman & Rahardjo, 2017; Sinha & Verma, 2018).

Meanwhile, the Point-of-Purchase (POP) material strategy plays a crucial role in Indomie's multi-channel marketing communications. POP materials, including special displays, promotional shelves, and banners installed at retail locations such as supermarkets and minimarkets, are designed with an attractive visual appeal. Both regular and variant product packaging are often displayed in bright colors and with catchy slogans to attract consumers' attention. For example, the Indomie Hype Abis display shelf, with its striking design and creative slogan, is a major draw for young consumers (Batt et al., 2021; Jin, 2017; Arthantri, 2021). Furthermore, in multi-channel campaigns, Indomie's POP materials are often combined with digital promotions on social media and e-commerce sites to create an integrated shopping experience. With an effective combination of sales promotion strategies and POP materials, Indomie is able to not only increase direct sales but also strengthen brand awareness and customer loyalty. Indomie consistently integrates digital and offline marketing communications through multi-channel channels, maintaining its relevance across various market segments. This success was also supported by a comprehensive approach to sponsorship activities, sales promotions, and optimization of POP materials linked to multi-channel campaigns (Syed, 2023; Vigna & Mainardes, 2019; Batt et al., 2021; Jin, 2017; Sinha & Verma, 2018). Thus, Indomie was able to maintain its position as the top brand of choice for consumers in the instant noodle market (Batt et al., 2021; Arthantri, 2021; Firman & Rahardjo, 2017).

Conventional and Contemporary Public Relations (PR 2.0)

Indomie leveraged contemporary PR (PR 2.0) with a robust strategy across various digital platforms. One approach was to launch a campaign on Instagram and TikTok using the hashtag #IndomieHypeAbis, which involved viral challenges like the "Hype Abis Dance Challenge." In this challenge, users showcased creative dance moves while demonstrating how to cook or enjoy the new variant.

To expand its reach, Indomie collaborated with popular celebrities like Arief Muhammad and Keanu Agl, who shared videos of themselves trying new flavors while providing humorous and relatable reviews. Additionally, food vlogger influencers like Ken & Grati contributed content featuring unique recipes using the "Hype Abis" variant, capturing the attention of an audience eager to explore culinary delights.

CRAZY SPICY INDOMIE HYPE ABIS!! 5 Packs of Mi Goreng Ramen Noodles | ...
135.7K views · May 19, 2019
YouTube · Peggie Neo

2 Indomie Hype Abis x 5 Telur Ceplok
3.6M views · Apr 3, 2019
YouTube · Korea Reomit

104.5M views · Nov 1, 2022
YouTube · Indomie

INDONESIA RASA CHITATO?!?! - Mie Indonesia HYPE ABIS
819.8K views · Sep 12, 2019
YouTube · NenuNeruSon

#KolabNtap Indomie Hype Abis Chitato
4.6M views · Jul 1, 2019
YouTube · Indomie

10 PACKS INDOMIE CHITATO MUKBANG
340.9K views · May 24, 2019
YouTube · Siaca Kohl

Indomie #HypeAbis Seblak Hot Jeletot & Indomie #HypeAbis Ayam Geprek yang ...
26.6M views · Oct 26, 2023
YouTube · Indomie

INDONESIA RASA CHITATO?!?!
1.8K views · May 24, 2019
YouTube · Kelvin Kurniawan

Indomie also encourages user-generated content by holding competitions on Instagram. In these competitions, fans are encouraged to upload creative photos or videos featuring "Hype Abis" products, such as showing off their coolest eating habits, to win exclusive merchandise. Furthermore, direct interaction with consumers is a key part of their strategy. On Twitter, the official @IndomieID account actively responds to consumer tweets in a relaxed and humorous manner. For example, when a user tweeted, "It's really spicy, like my ex," the official account replied, "It's really hype, different from my ex who's just ordinary." This strategy strengthens engagement and builds a stronger emotional connection with consumers.

Web & Social Media Management in Integrated Marketing Communications

Indomie's official website provides a dedicated page for the "Hype Abis" edition, which includes detailed descriptions of flavors like "Pedas Asam" and "Spicy Roast Beef." The page also features interactive video tutorials on unique preparations, such as "Hype Abis Dalgona Noodles." Additionally, it displays information about current promotions, such as special discounts for purchases through partner e-commerce platforms like Shopee and Tokopedia. Countdown timer widgets for limited-time promotions, such as "Get Indomie Hype Abis for only Rp10,000 for 24 hours," add to the page's appeal. Consumers can also fill out a simple form to leave a review of the new flavor or suggest other variants.

Digital-based Social Marketing Communication

Indomie integrates elements of support for local MSMEs through its digital campaigns. One initiative is the "Hype Lokal" program, which involves collaborating with small food vendors on social media to create signature Indomie-based menus called "Hype Abis." For example, a vendor on TikTok created a cooking video featuring "Martabak Hype Abis," which was then picked up by Indomie's official account, boosting the MSME's visibility. In addition, Indomie launched a donation campaign, where a portion of the proceeds from the sale of the "Hype Abis" variant were distributed to support creative education programs for young people. This campaign used social media to encourage consumers to actively participate. The "Hype Abis" campaign successfully captured the attention of a young audience by capitalizing on digital culture trends. For example, Indomie used a "Hype Culture"-themed meme with a retro 2000s visual style popular in online communities. The language used in this campaign also aligns with youth communication trends, such as the use of phrases such as "You absolutely must try this to avoid FOMO!" and "Guaranteed to make your tongue go crazy!" which frequently appear in Instagram and Twitter posts. Indomie leverages the power of social media to spread its brand message through digital campaigns. One example is the "Hype Community" challenge on TikTok, which involved various communities, including street dance and graffiti artists, to create creative content themed around Indomie's "Hype Abis" brand. This content went viral after being reposted by other users eager to join in the trend.

Additionally, Indomie encouraged consumers to create user-generated content by uploading creative photos or videos featuring "Hype Abis" products using the hashtag #GenerasiHype. Each post garnered widespread attention, strengthening the organic spread of the brand's message.

Indomie Digital Marketing Communication

Business to Business (B2B)

The growing role of B2B marketing in recent times can certainly support businesses and provide added value. According to the latest B2B buyer research published by DemandGen Report, the world of B2B marketing continues to become more complex, and buyers are becoming more sophisticated. Several survey results indicate (Agus Wibowo, 2023):

1. More than half (56 percent) of companies have four or more people involved in purchasing decisions, while 21 percent have seven or more stakeholders;
2. 75 percent of shoppers say they spend more time researching purchases, up from 72 percent in 2018;
3. 79 percent of respondents said the winning vendor's content had a significant impact on their final purchasing decision. How did the commercial transaction occur?

between business to business can be in the form of B2B trading environment, business markets, trading partnerships and digital marketing strategies.

In a B2B context, Indomie can use digital marketing communications to reach resellers, such as distributors, wholesalers, or large agents who will resell Indomie products. It can also communicate with restaurants, supermarkets, or business partners for bulk purchases. Finally, Indomie can leverage digital marketing, such as email marketing or LinkedIn, to deliver special offers or introduce new products. However, there will be limitations that

can be faced, such as the more specific B2B audience, such as distributors and retailers, then the focus of B2B communication itself which is more about building long-term relationships, and also B2B which usually emphasizes efficiency in financial terms.

Business to Consumer (B2C) & Consumer to Business (C2B)

Business to Consumer (B2C) is a retail model that processes the sale of products and services directly from business actors to consumers as end users who purchase products or services for personal use where there is no intermediary between the company and the consumer (Adhitya Wardhana, 2020). When compared, it turns out that Indomie is not entirely suitable for implementing digital marketing communications in the Business to Business (B2B) model as the main strategy, because the nature of the product and its target market are more relevant to the Business to Consumer (B2C) model. Here are some reasons why Indomie is more relevant to the B2C model:

1. Products for End Consumers

Indomie is a daily consumption product that is directly used by individual consumers, not in the form of raw materials or production tools that a company needs to run their business operations.

2. Digital Platform Channels

Social media platforms like TikTok, Instagram, YouTube, X, and Facebook are excellent platforms for conveying messages and campaigns about Indomie products. Examples include Indomie Hype Abis, viral Indomie challenges, and testimonials from public figures, celebrities, and influencers.

3. The Purchasing Process and Cultural Emotions

Indomie purchasing decisions are influenced by habits, promotions, and emotional appeal. Marketing communications based on storytelling and creativity are effective in directly driving purchases.

Furthermore, Consumer-to-Business (C2B) marketing communications are also suitable for Indomie, where consumers provide value to the company in a digital marketing context. Increasing reviews and testimonials organically can enhance brand credibility and spread the promotion organically based on positive consumer experiences. Indomie can also gather feedback from consumers to innovate, develop new flavors, or refine existing ones that could be further improved.

By combining the B2C and C2B models for Indomie, you will get several benefits such as:

1. Increased Brand Engagement

Consumer engagement through C2B as well as direct purchasing in B2C marketing will create a closer relationship between customers and the Indomie brand.

2. Viral and Organic Effects

Consumer-generated content that goes viral on social media can expand Indomie's reach organically and without additional costs.

3. Consumer Loyalty

By listening to and responding to feedback from consumers, it will certainly strengthen emotional connections and loyalty to the Indomie brand.

Then, to determine the right program strategy for business to consumer or consumer to business, it is necessary to have a proper understanding of the target audience and use the right channels. For more details, it is as follows:

1. Target Audience

How to determine the target audience from its demographics such as young people, students, workers, families who need fast and affordable food, can also be based on characteristics such as culinary lovers, noodle lovers or practical food lovers.

2. Digital Channels

After that, you can choose the right digital channel with the identified audience, such as social media such as Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, and Facebook, which reach a wide audience for Indomie marketing.

3. Influencer Marketing

The use of influencers and public figures can also make their loyal fans interested and want to try what their idols recommend.

4. Ads Marketing

Using Instagram ads, TikTok ads, Facebook ads, and Google ads can also help promote new products or special promotions.

5. Emotional Marketing Messages

The message of nostalgia, comfort and deliciousness of Indomie plus a strong tagline such as Indomie Hype Abis can strengthen the emotional connection for consumers.

6. E-commerce

The ease of transactions in using the right E-Commerce such as Shopee, Tokopedia, Blibli is suitable for direct purchases for consumers, plus there are different and attractive promotions.

7. Customer Support

Consumer feedback on social media and product reviews on e-commerce platforms can improve product and service quality. Promptly addressing customer complaints demonstrates that customers' voices are valued. Furthermore, responding to customer comments and offering insightful ideas or reviews can be beneficial.

8. Digital Community

By building a digital community such as the Indomie lovers community on social media such as Facebook groups or others by sharing recipes, stories can strengthen the emotional connection between the brand and customers.

9. Evaluation and Optimization

Conduct an evaluation of the campaign that has been carried out by measuring total engagement and sales in the market.

With the existence of complementary B2B and B2C digital marketing communications, consumers can be directly involved and can also become material for innovation and improvement based on customer input in order to maintain loyalty to the brand so that Indomie continues to exist, innovate and connect with its customers in the digital world.

CONCLUSION

Indomie's multi-channel digital marketing strategy, implemented through the "Hype Abis" campaign, has proven effective in increasing consumer engagement, strengthening brand awareness, and driving sales growth. The campaign's success is inseparable from the integrated use of various digital channels that support each other in delivering marketing messages to the target audience. Social media integration, particularly through Instagram and TikTok, enabled Indomie to build creative, interactive, and participatory communications with the younger audience segment. Digital challenge-based campaigns, such as the "Mi Goreng Challenge," and the use of the hashtag #IndomieHypeAbis, successfully created a significant viral effect and increased widespread user engagement. Furthermore, collaboration with influencers and food vloggers played a key role in creating authentic and persuasive promotions. The presence of figures who are close to the audience increased consumer trust in the brand while expanding the reach of the marketing message. Creative content presented through an emotional storytelling approach, strong visual branding, and the utilization of digital cultural trends helped Indomie convey brand values in a relevant and engaging manner to the target market. In terms of sales conversion, utilizing e-commerce platforms such as Shopee and Tokopedia through special discount and promotion strategies proved effective in driving a 15% increase in sales during the campaign period. Not only focusing on consumer acquisition, this campaign also succeeded in increasing customer loyalty through active consumer participation in the form of user-generated content (Consumer to Business/C2B) and positive reviews that strengthen the emotional connection between the brand and consumers. This is reflected in the 12% increase in consumer loyalty after the campaign was implemented. Overall, the success of the "Hype Abis" campaign confirms that the combination of Business to Consumer (B2C) and Consumer to Business (C2B) strategies can provide an optimal impact on the growth and strengthening of the Indomie brand. Evaluation of campaign performance conducted through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), such as engagement rate, online sales, and user participation levels, is a key factor in ensuring the effectiveness of the implemented digital marketing communication strategy. Based on the evaluation results, the development of Indomie's future digital marketing communication strategy needs to be directed towards the use of technological innovation and a more data-driven approach. One strategic recommendation is to adopt augmented reality (AR) technology to create a more immersive consumer experience through interactive features, such as instant noodle preparation tutorials or cooking simulations for new product variants. This technology is expected to increase consumer engagement while strengthening Indomie's image as an innovative brand.

Furthermore, optimizing collaboration with influencers requires a data-driven, analytical approach to identify influencers whose audiences align with Indomie's target market. This approach allows the company to build more strategic, effective collaborations that directly impact engagement and sales conversions. Developing a digital loyalty program is also crucial, with the goal of designing an app-based system or digital platform that offers various incentives, such as special discounts, exclusive gifts, or access to limited-edition campaigns, to maintain long-term

consumer loyalty. Furthermore, Indomie is advised to expand its marketing approach to the Business-to-Business (B2B) segment by utilizing professional platforms, such as LinkedIn and email marketing, to establish more effective communication with distributors, restaurants, and supermarket chains. Exclusive offers in the form of product bundling promotions and wholesale discounts have the potential to expand distribution channels and strengthen Indomie's position in the B2B market. By consistently implementing these recommendations, Indomie is expected to increase its competitiveness in the increasingly competitive digital market, expand its audience reach, and maintain its position as the market leader for instant noodles in Indonesia. Technology integration and continuous innovation will be key to the success of Indomie's future marketing strategy.

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